

QUASI-THREE-DIMENSIONAL COMPOSITES FOR AEROSPACE APPLICATIONS

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SUMMARY

Based on a three-dimensional networking and an overlapping/offset mechanism, several innovative quasi-three-dimensional (Q3D) composites with high delamination resistance and adequate in-plane properties were developed for aerospace structure applications. For demonstration purpose, manufacturing procedures for the Q3D composites were developed and presented in this manuscript.

Keywords: aerospace structures, quasi-three-dimensional networking, overlapping/offset mechanism, in-plane properties, delamination resistance

QUASI-THREE-DIMENSIONAL COMPOSITES

Background

Fiber-reinforced polymer-matrix composite laminates have been commonly used in aerospace structures due to their high in-plane stiffness and in-plane strength with low density. However, they are susceptible to delamination when subjected to transverse loading such as bending and transverse impact. The former may occur in riveting, resulting in local delamination around the mechanical fasteners, while the latter may take place due to collision with birds and runway debris, resulting in large-area delamination and even perforation in the composite laminates.

The cause of delamination is due to mismatch of material properties through the laminates. In order to achieve high stiffness and high strength with low density, materials are made in fiber form which has much smaller defects than the same materials in bulk form. Fiber bundles are then integrated with a matrix to form a unidirectional composite layer. This composite layer, however, is less stiff and less strong in the directions away from the fiber direction since its properties in the directions away from the fiber direction become more affected by the matrix, which has much lower stiffness and strength than the fibers. In order to improve the weak properties away from the fiber direction, composite layers of various fiber orientations are laminated together, resulting in a composite laminate. Similar to the unidirectional composite layers, in which fibers are bonded by matrix, a composite laminate is also bonded together by matrix through the laminate thickness. Hence the out-of-plane properties of composite laminates are expected to be much lower than the in-plane counterparts.

Besides the inherent weak link based on matrix among composite layers, the mismatch of in-plane fiber orientations can also amplify the out-of-plane weakness. When subjected to an in-plane force, the composite layers of a composite laminate with different fiber orientations will deform in different manners and additional out-of-plane stresses will be induced in order to maintain the equilibrium of the composite laminate. If the out-of-plane stresses, i.e. interlaminar stresses, are higher than the matrix strength, delamination will occur. A similar phenomenon can also be seen in composite laminates loaded by out-of-plane forces, such as bending and transverse impact. That is, due to the mismatch of bending stiffness caused by different fiber orientations in different layers, composite laminates can experience high interlaminar stresses and result in delamination.

Once delamination takes place, a composite laminate can suffer a significant loss of integrity. For example, when a composite laminate is delaminated, its resistance to penetration by foreign objects will be greatly reduced since the foreign objects will not have to break the fibers which hold the primary strength of the composite. Instead, they can simply push the fibers aside as they move into the laminate.

Another reason which ironically helps raise the attention of delamination is the unaccessibility of the damage mode. Delamination is usually not visible and hard to detect in composite laminates. When delamination takes place, the composite laminates may appear to be intact. The hidden damage may mislead composite engineers from taking any early necessary action before the catastrophic failure takes place. Various non-destructive evaluation techniques have been made available, however, more accurate and efficient techniques are still needed to be developed.

In combating delamination, several techniques have been proposed and used in the composite community. Stitching and z-pinning are the two most commonly used techniques. However, their effects on the composite reinforcement are controversial due likely to the damage they also introduce to the composite materials. When a composite laminate is reinforced with a stitch or a z-pin, the reinforcing materials can be considered like the pin or bolt in mechanical fastening. It is aligned in the thickness direction and loaded in the plane. Accordingly, high stress concentration can take place around the stitching line or the z-pin.

Another technique for combating delamination is the use woven composites. Two-dimensional (2D) woven composites such as those based on plain weaves have been demonstrated to be superior to their laminated counterparts in combating delamination. Their superiority can also be understood based on the concept of material mismatch. When a 2D woven composite based on plain weave is fabricated, the difference of material properties among layers becomes much smaller than that in the laminated counterpart. That is, the induction of interlaminar stresses due to the difference caused by in-plane mismatch should become smaller. The only weakness remained in the 2D woven composite will then be the weak matrix on the composite interfaces.

Although 2D woven composites have higher delamination resistance than their laminated counterparts, they still suffer the inherent weakness on the matrix-based interfaces. Three-dimensional (3D) woven composites which are based on fiber yarns in all three directions should solve the delamination issue significantly. However, most composite materials are primarily used for in-plane loading. This is particularly true in the aerospace industry. For example, the fuselages are pressurized at high altitudes and

the wings are subjected to constant bending during flights. Hence, the fiber yarns in the thickness direction (z-direction) are not as important as the in-plane yarns in supporting the membrane loads. In fact, they can cause high local stresses similarly to those caused by stitching threads and z-pins.

It now becomes clear that an ideal composite material for aerospace structures should have high in-plane stiffness and high delamination resistance. The objective of this study is to present a new class of composite materials, namely quasi-three-dimensional (Q3D) composite, to achieve the goal, combating delamination while maintaining high in-plane properties.

Quasi-three-dimensional Networking

The novel Q3D composites [1-3] are defined to be woven composites with all layers interwoven in a gradual manner as shown in Figure 1. A casual way to describe the Q3D composites is to emphasize that the adjacent layers are woven together, i.e. the first layer weaves with the second layer and the second layer weaves with the third layers, so on and so forth until all layers are interwoven together. Interlayer weaving seems to be another term to describe this class of woven composites.

Figure 1 – Quasi-three-dimensional woven composite.

On one side, the Q3D composites are very different from the conventional three-dimensional (3D) composites since there is no fiber yarns aligned in the thickness direction. On the other side, the Q3D composites are similar to 3D composites because all the yarns in a Q3D composite form a three-dimensional network. Consequently, high delamination resistance can be achieved through the quasi-three-dimensional weaving. In addition, due to the small undulation involved in the layer networking, because the undulation in the Q3D composites is no higher than the thickness of two yarns, the

reduction of in-plane properties due to undulation caused by the Q3D weaving should not be too greater than the conventional composite laminates.

High-Harness with Overlapping /Offset Mechanism

In order to achieve high in-plane properties for Q3D composites, it is essentially important to keep the weaving yarns as flat as possible. Several methods have been demonstrated to be capable of achieving high level of flatness, subsequently high in-plane properties. They are: thinner yarns, larger weaving cells, smaller undulation zone, and higher harness. The yarn thickness is dependent on the availability of composite materials and cannot be changed arbitrarily. The cell size is tied to scaling effect. Any change may cause chain effects. The length of undulation zone requires an advanced manufacturing technique, such as an efficient beating technique. The high harness seems to be the most convenient and controllable method for improving layer flatness and is considered in this study.

Besides the undulation (waviness) of layers in woven composites, another inherent defect of woven composite is the resin rich corners, or resin-rich pockets. In order to further minimize this defect in high harness composites, an innovative weaving technique, so-called overlapping/offset weaving, was also developed in this study. Instead of weaving the Q3D composites with all cells and weaving corners perfectly aligned through the thickness, adjacent layers in the thickness direction were shifted, or offset, by a distance half the length of the weaving cell, resulting in overlapping weaves in which the subsequent layer in the thickness direction covered the layer boundaries and weaving corners of the current layer, resulting in a composite with much higher level of uniformity. Both the mechanisms of high harness and overlapping/offset weaving were used in this study. Accordingly, composites with higher level of flatness as well as higher level of uniform properties can be achieved. They are obvious advantages to aerospace structures subjected to aerodynamic effect and uniform loading.

MANUFACTURING TECHNIQUES

In order to demonstrate the manufacturability of the Q3D design, several Q3D woven composites were prepared manually. In the demonstration, strips of unidirectional yarns 9.5mm (0.375") wide were cut from a glass/epoxy prepreg tape. The tape came as a long roll of 30mm (12") width with continuous glass fibers aligned along the length of the tape and impregnated with an epoxy matrix. The tape was backed by a waxed paper which kept the layers of the roll from sticking to one another. It was constantly sealed inside an airtight bag to keep moisture away when it was not in use. The bag was stored in a freezer until the prepreg tape was to be used. This prevented the epoxy matrix from becoming sticky and beginning to cure. When the tape was to be used, the bag was removed from the freezer and allowed to defrost to room temperature for about an hour. The reason for keeping the bag sealed till the tape was at room temperature was to make sure that condensate was not allowed to form on the prepreg tape.

Once at room temperature for about an hour, the prepreg tape with the backing material still on was removed from the bag. It unrolled on a cutting mat one length at a time and

cut into pieces based on the size of sample to be made. In this study, it was decided to prepare each sample individually, as opposed to prepare a large panel and from which samples were cut. This one-sample-at-a-time process also made the weaving less cumbersome and caused less harmful manipulation to the yarns.

The prepreg tape was cut into strips using a rotary cutter. This was better than using a scissor or blade as this did not pull or deform the fabric during cutting. A dimensioned cutting mat was also proved to be helpful when cutting pieces of specific dimension. It was also important to handle the prepreg tape in a room with lower temperature, such as 60°F. When the temperature of a room became warmer, the prepreg tape would become stickier and softer and more difficult to handle. On the contrary, when the room became cooler, the prepreg tape would become drier and less sticky and the prepreg roll would be stiffer and easier to manipulate during weaving. Besides, it was considered to be a good practice to cut many pieces of the prepreg tape at a time from the parent roll and stored them in separate bags. This practice prevented the main roll from having to be defrosted every time a piece was needed which would cause the degradation of the composite tape due to thermal cycling. And the small bags of cut pieces would also take less time to defrost than the whole prepreg roll.

In preparing weaving strips, each cut prepreg piece was placed with the stickier side down on the cutting board and cut along the fiber direction into strips which would serve as individual yarns in the weave. Experience showed that the right angle scale being used as a guide for the cutter should be placed slightly above the prepreg and not touching it, otherwise it tended to stick to and damage the material. Several prepreg pieces were cut into strips and the strips for one session of weaving were stored inside an airtight bag. Details of some weaving patterns are given below. Once each specimen was prepared, it was placed in between two waxed paper sheets and stored in an airtight bag in the freezer till a whole batch was ready for curing.

In this study, three types of weaving procedures were used based on the type of weave. In the case of the two-dimensional weaves, i.e. 2D, several layers were produced individually and then placed over one another with the required alignment. For the higher harness quasi-three-dimensional weaves, such as Q3DO5, the specimen was built up one layer at a time, with the new layer being formed and integrated into the lower layer and thus into the entire sample. In the case of quasi-three-dimensional plain weaves without high harness, i.e. Q3D, this method was not feasible as the manipulations required to pull the yarns of the underlying layers would cause significant damage and hence affect the accuracy of the weave. In this case, the specimen was built from center of the specimen outwards with all layers through the thickness at a cross section being produced simultaneously.

2D Plain Weaves

The simplest type of weaving pattern is for two-dimensional plain weave, i.e. 2D weave. The weaving procedures are given below and depicted in Figure 2.

1. First the yarns of the warp direction were laid down on an adhesive strip to hold them in position.
2. It proved to be easier to carry out the next steps if the tapes were placed with their stickier sides facing up. Using raiser, the alternate yarns were split. The raiser was used to gently push back to create adequate place for the weft yarn to fit. Due to the stiffness of the yarns, they held their position long enough to carry out the next steps. The weft yarn was inserted into the gap, and brought as close to its final position as possible.
3. The raiser was slid up to support the gap wide enough so that a blade edge could help with 'packing' the yarn as tightly into the wedge. If this was done with care, no damage was caused to the tape.
4. Now the next set of alternate yarns was raised and the procedure repeated.

This method could also be used for 2D weaves of any harness number.

Figure 2 Weaving Procedures for 2D plain weaves.

High Harness Q3D Weaves

For high harness Q3D weaves, a layerwise approach was adopted as every new layer was integrated into the previous topmost layer. Figure 3 describes the steps involved in the first few layers of a five harness Q3D weave, i.e. Q3DO5. The process could be just repeated for as many layers as needed. It should be mentioned though, that the difficulty involved increased with the number of layers as there was some amount of 'give' that was required from the already formed weave so that yarns could be inserted without damaging the weave. As the number of yarns in the whole system increased and owing to their slight stickiness, the weave became less pliable.

1. The first layer of any Q3D weave would resemble a 2D weave of that harness number. This was produced in the same way as with the 2D plain weave.
2. Now the next layer had to be integrated with the topmost woven layer. In high harness offset weaves like Q3DO5, the new layer yarns would be introduced below (for weaving) and in the middle (for offsetting) of the long free harness of the layer below. The yarn was introduced by carefully prying the lower yarn span open with the tool and sliding the new yarn in while simultaneously sliding the tool out. In Figure 3 it might appear that the yarn is being unduly stretched, but in reality the whole weave deflects a bit. The yarn being lifted will slide a bit out but once the step is complete, it can be nudged back into its original position.
3. Once the weaving of the current layer was completed, the next set of yarns was introduced similarly at 90 degrees to the last set for orthogonal weaves.

Figure 3 High Harness Q3D Weaves.

Q3D Plain Weaves

The samples of Q3D plain weaves require the most amount of dexterity to weave as weaving of complete thickness is done simultaneously at any cross section. Figure 4 shows the weaving procedures.

1. First, each yarn needed to be 'capped' with tape. This was to prevent the yarns from sticking together and to facilitate easy splitting of the yarns when inserting the cross yarns. This also made it easier to differentiate between layers when many yarns, such as six, were dealt with simultaneously.

2. The weaving was begun from the center of the sample. The center four yarns (all six layers) were placed as shown. In this case, the stickiness of the yarns was used to an advantage. After each set of yarns was set, they could be pressed a bit which held them together well, making further manipulation less delicate.

3. Now the weave was formed step by step going outwards in all directions. A tool was used to split and hold apart the yarns while the cross yarns were inserted, starting from the bottom yarn in a set and moving upwards. The exploded view in Figure 4 shows the cross section of the area being woven at that point and the way in which the yarns need to be separated in order to achieve a Q3D weave. Once the entire sample was formed, the edges of the yarns with the tape were cut off so that the tape did not go into the curing process.

The weaving procedures for the smaller angle weaves were similar to the above methods for their respective weave types, with the obvious change in angle of insertion of cross yarns.

Figure 4 Q3D plain weaves.

Curing

The curing process involved removing the bagged specimens from the freezer and letting them defrost to room temperature without the bags being opened for the same reason as before. The specimens were then placed in a sealed bag within several layers of materials (Figure 5). The perforated mylar was to make releasing the specimens easy, while still allowing excess resin to flow to and get absorbed by the breather sheets. This whole layup was placed in a hot press and a pressure of 560 kPa (80 psi) was applied to the specimens. The temperature was ramped up to 320°F at 10°F/minute. It was held at

this temperature for 45 minutes before being ramped back down to room temperature at the same rate. The specimens were removed and were now ready for testing.

IN-PLANE STIFFNESS AND DELAMINATION RESISTANCE

The Q3D woven composites, including Q3D[0/90]₆, Q3DO3[0/90]₆ (three harness with offset) and Q3DO5[0/90]₆ (five harness with offset) were examined with low-velocity impact for its delamination resistance and energy absorption capability. They were also examined by compression testing before and after impact to identify the in-plane stiffness, buckling resistance and damage tolerance. The results of the Q3D composites were compared with those of laminated L[0/90]₆ and two-dimensional plain weaves 2D[0/90]₆.

In-plane Stiffness

The in-plane stiffness of the composites investigated reduced from L to 2D then to Q3D while it increased from Q3D to Q3DO3 then to Q3DO5. The reduction was clearly due to the increase of undulation of fiber yarns and the increase was also clearly due to the reduction of undulation.

Delamination Resistance

The delamination area of the composites investigated reduced from L to 2D then to Q3D while it increased from Q3D to Q3DO3 then to Q3DO5. The reduction was clearly due to the increase of undulation barrier provided by fiber yarns and the increase was also clearly due to the reduction of undulation barrier.

This study provides a way to improve the delamination resistance of composite materials while maintaining adequate in-plane properties.

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References

1. Coppens, George J., "Effects of Three-dimensional Geometry on Penetration and Perforation Resistance," M.S. thesis, Michigan State University, May, 2004.
2. Coppens, G.C. and Liu, D., "Effects of Though-Thickness Fiber Geometry and Small Angle on Impact Resistance," *J. Adavanced Materials*, 39(4), 44-54, 2007.
3. Rosario, K., "Testing of Quasi-three-dimensional Composite Materials," M.S. thesis, Michigan State University, July, 2008.